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**CALIBRATION OF DETAILED BUILDING ENERGY MODELS USING A
HYBRID MODELLING APPROACH.**

General comments of the task:

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1. TABLE OF ACRONYMS

ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers
BEMS	Building energy management system
BES	Building energy simulation
BESS	Building energy simulation software
BIM	Building Information Management
BLC	Building life-cycle
COP	Coefficient of performance
CVRMSE	Coefficient of variation of the mean square error
EiT	Energy in time
GAs	Genetic algorithms
HX	Heat exchanger
IBPSA	International Building Performance Simulation Association
IES-VE	Integrated Environmental Solutions Virtual Environment
LAT	Leaving air temperature
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
M&V	Measurement and Verification
NMBE	Normalised mean bias error
RAT	Return air temperature
SAT	Supply air temperature
STEM	Short-term end-use monitoring

2. ABSTRACT

Building Energy Simulation (BES) tools are typically used to forecast the energy demand of buildings during the design or the operational stage. Building Energy Performance Simulations (BEPS) software such as EnergyPlus and IES Virtual Environment (IES-VE) allow us to create both types of models. Models of existing buildings can be used to forecast the building energy demand under different retrofit or control strategy scenarios, but require calibration in order to achieve accurate results.

Model calibration is currently a challenging task in the industry due to high computational costs, lack of quantitative and qualitative data, the technical expertise required, and the lack of automation. This work presents a methodology to tackle these limitations using a hybrid approach consisting of five steps: (1) sensitivity analysis, (2) space and zone level calibration, (3) component level calibration, (4) system level calibration and, (5) measurement and verification (M&V). Each step requires data inputs that can be measured or derived, but some inputs are not economically feasible to obtain. To address this, measured data is utilized to improve estimates for missing inputs that cannot be commonly measured in real buildings, such as infiltration, occupancy profile and coefficient of performance (COP). Measured data is taken from the Building Energy Management System (BEMS) and other sensors installed in the building whereas missing inputs are obtained using genetic algorithms (GAs). The objective of this approach is having a model accurate enough to explore building control strategies with an hourly resolution.

A hotel in Finland is presented as case study. The calibration is done on an hourly basis and the absolute calibration error the model is 2.42% for the heating coil loads, other measurement and verification (M&V) indices are used to assess the level of calibration. Time lags, temperature damping, forecasting occupancy, infiltration patterns in hourly-resolution models and uncertainty are important limitations of this approach. In conclusion, the benefit of having a calibrated model surpasses the effort required in the methodology presented in this work.

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5. OBJECTIVES

5.1. General objectives

- Present and assess a calibration methodology for models with hourly data resolution using a five-stage approach and a derivation process with genetic algorithms (GAs) optimisation.

5.2. Specific objectives

- Deliver a summary of the current calibration approaches;
- Document the current Measurement and Verification (M&V) criteria from different standards and international organisations;
- Develop a detailed approach for multi-stage simulation calibration;
- Comprehensively report the best practices to obtain the required data from the building.
- Contribute to the reduction of time/costs related to model calibration;
- Provide a documentation of the calibration process using this approach to work as a guideline for practitioners;
- Illustrate the importance of calibrated model in the reduction of energy consumption in buildings;
- Present and M&V criteria for air temperature readings;
- Recognise and shed light on the limitations of the presented calibration approach.

6. GENERAL METHODOLOGY

This work emerges from the need for having an hourly-resolution calibrated model used for the development of scenarios for building operation control strategies to reduce the energy demand, as part of an EU research project called Energy-in-Time (EiT).

The following chart explains how the project was realized divided into high-level steps.

Figure 1: General methodology of the workflow for realising the method used.

The approximated time required for each of these steps is illustrated in the following table. In total, six months were required in order to identify the problem, recognise the current calibration methodologies that consultants use, develop a methodology, adapt software to test the approach, proceed with the calibration and test the results using standards for calibration performance.

Table 1: General methodology timeline.

Task	Time (months)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
General methodology						
Identification the need (EiT scope)						
Explore current calibration approaches.						
Check how practitioners do						
Identification of the problem (excessive manual work)						
Propose a methodology						
Manage to get the proper software tools						
Test methodology with a case study						
Assess pros and cons of the proposed solution						
Discussion about future work						

Finally, in the chart below each chapter is briefly described.

<p>Introduction</p>	<p>Impact of buildings in the CO₂ emissions in Europe followed by an overview of building energy simulations and software;</p> <hr/> <p>Building Energy Simulation (BES) and IES Virtual Environment software description;</p> <hr/> <p>EU funded project: 'Energy in time' aiming to use energy simulations for building control operations.</p>
<p>Literature review</p>	<p>A brief explanation of the type of the building energy simulation models;</p> <hr/> <p>Understanding the difference between design simulation and calibrated simulation;</p> <hr/> <p>Present Measurement and Verification (M&V) standards.</p> <hr/> <p>Genetic algorithms (GAs)</p>
<p>Proposed methodology</p>	<p>Explanation of the building levels and the type of data required for each level;</p> <hr/> <p>High level of methodology steps and data gathering recommendations;</p>
<p>Case study: LEVI (Hotel)</p>	<p>Description of building levels;</p> <hr/> <p>Model development and calibration;</p> <hr/> <p>M&V results.</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>Conclusions, discussion, limitations and future work.</p>

Figure 2: Summary of the contents found in each chapter.

7. INTRODUCTION

Buildings account for 40% of the overall energy usage and 40% of the CO₂ emissions in Europe (Zhao & Magoulès, 2012). Due to the role that the built environment is playing in the greenhouse gas emissions, the reduction or mitigation of its energy demand has been critical to avoid the 2-degree rise in the average temperature worldwide, as outlined in Paris climate change agreement in 2015 (United Nations, 2015).

The European Commission estimates that residential and commercial European buildings have a potential of energy savings about 26% and 30% respectively (European Commission, 2007). This can be achieved by increasing energy consumption efficiency and the deployment of renewable energy resources.

“The cleanest energy is the one you don't use” (Vandomel, 2014), based on this premise, the efficient energy exploitation in buildings is the most important strategy to reduce CO₂ emissions in Europe. Building Energy Simulation (BES) tools can play a key role in achieving this reduction, by exploiting their ability to forecast the impact of changes to building fabric and controls, and thus aiding the selection of optimal solutions for both new and existing buildings.

7.1. Building energy simulations

BES as a decision-making tool, represents a unique opportunity to achieve energy saving by scenario simulation. Models don't predict the future, but rather “multiple futures” (Krenchel & Madsbjerg, 2014), however the likelihood of these “futures” or scenarios, will be subject to the quality of the inputs. BES are used to forecast the energy demand in both new and existing buildings and the recent utilisation of this technology is already reducing energy demand in buildings, enabling renewable energy sources to be more cost-effective. This tool can be used not only in single buildings but it can be extrapolated to neighbourhood, district or city level. BES enables architects and engineers to forecast the impact of the design and choice of materials on the energy consumption throughout the lifespan of the building. Furthermore, it predicts the effectiveness of the implementation of renewables,

defines the capacity of heating and air-conditioning systems, benefits in the improvement of the indoor comfort, etc. This topic is further developed in the literature review.

However, the reliability of any model is in risk due to its level of uncertainty. Performance gaps are commonly found in models regardless the size of the project, caused mostly by faults in the design, construction and operation. It is always expected to have a difference between the modelled and the actual performance, however, this difference should be minimized in order to maximise the usefulness of the building energy simulations (Dirkes & Weaver, 2016).

7.2. Building energy simulation software (BESS)

There are many building simulation tools available for both commercial and research purposes, some of which perform specialized functions. For whole building energy simulation tools, the following are the most widely used in both industry and academia:

- EnergyPlus (Strand, 2001)
- IES-VE
- ESP-r (Energy Systems Research Unit, 1974)
- DesignBuilder (EnergyPlus engine)
- Modelica
- Sefaira
- TRNSYS (Fiksel, Thornton, Klein, & Beckman, 1995).
- IDA ICE
- TAS

More BESS are listed in the IBPSA-USA website¹ and thorough reviews of the current building energy simulation software are presented in the work of (Reddy, 2006) and (Crawley, Hand, Kummert, & Griffith, 2008).

¹ <http://www.buildingenergysoftwaretools.com/>

Among the available software options, the IES virtual environment (IES-VE), is a commercial software consisting of several applications that work together for the building energy simulations. IES-VE allows advanced building simulation control as well as the use of measured data for the model both as inputs and outputs for the M&V process. Three subprograms of the IES-VE are critical for the building calibration process: Apache HVAC, SCAN and Optimise.

7.2.1. ApacheHVAC

Apache HVAC, as shown in Figure 3, is a graphical representation of the HVAC networks designed to simulate the building control strategies as well as to assess the current ones to detect opportunities for the energy reduction. During the design stage of the building, this software is also used for auto-sizing the different components and pumps' capacity is needed. For the calibration stage, controllers, fans, heating and cooling coils, heat exchangers, can be simulated being able to imitate the real building control strategies for advanced calibration and simulations results can be displayed for each of the components alongside measured data.

Figure 3: Representation of a HVAC network in the Virtual Environment. Source: IES-VE

It is worth describing each of the main elements that are part of a HVAC network as well as the symbols used to represent them throughout this work, this is done in Table 2 .

Table 2: Description of the main elements of the HVAC network in Apache HVAC. Source: Pictures from IES-VE

Element	Description	Icon
Heating coils	Heat from the hot water loop is transferred to the air in this device.	
Cooling coil	Heat from the air is absorbed by the chilled water loop, cooling down the air.	
Heat exchanger/ Enthalpy wheel	Enthalpy from the exhaust air is transferred to fresh air reducing the need for heating/cooling	
Fans	Air fans to circulate the air through the HVAC network.	
Air ducts	These elements represent the heat exchange with the rooms where the ducts pass by.	
Independent controller	Used to determine airflow or heating/cooling set-points using absolute values.	
Dependent controller	Used to determine airflow or heating/cooling set-points depending on other conditions such as outdoor air temperature or return air temperature.	

<p>Zone</p>	<p>Represents a group of rooms conditioned by the same HVAC network.</p>	
<p>Water pump</p>	<p>Water pump circulates water through the hot/chilled water loops. Other liquids can be considered such as glycol.</p>	
<p>Radiator</p>	<p>Is a device used to transfer heat as radiation/convection directly from hot water loops.</p>	
<p>Heat source</p>	<p>Most of the time represents the transformation from primary energy sources (as found in nature) to secondary ones such as heat or electricity. A coefficient of performance (< 1) is required.</p>	
<p>Heat pump</p>	<p>Represents a device used to transfer heat from two areas with different temperatures through a mechanical cycle. Used both for cooling and heating. Coefficient of performance is required, usually around 3.</p>	

7.2.2. SCAN

SCAN is a cloud based data platform which enables the integration of measured data to the building models through free form profiles (*.ffp)². Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the data gathering for a heat meter. By using this platform, measured data from real buildings can be directly exported to the model in the IES-VE as time-series data increasing the accuracy of the model. If the readings are “inputs” they will override the standard model assumptions such as equipment gain. On the other hand, if they are “outputs” they can be directly compared and assessed with any simulation result available in the model.

Figure 4: SCAN online platform containing the variables used in the model as inputs for the simulation as well as outputs for M&V. Source: IES-VE

7.2.3. Optimise

Optimise is a multi-objective tool optimisation based on genetic algorithms (GAs) that is able to modify not only physical characteristics of the model such as conductivity and U-values, but also occupancy and infiltration profiles during a given calibration period to minimise the error between simulated and measured time-series data (Aird, 2016). Occupancy and infiltration described by a free-form-profile can be optimised based on measured data of a distinct nature. For instance, the typical occupancy profile for a zone in a model is shown in Figure 5. Optimise reads the free-

² Product information available at:
<http://www.emxlondon.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/IES-SCAN-Flyer-Aug141.pdf>

form-profile linked to occupancy and each different value of each day is turned into a model parameter.

Figure 5: Typical profile for occupancy for a restaurant, which can be optimised to match air temperature, loads or energy measurements. Source: IES-VE.

For this case, 4 parameters (0, 0.25, 0.50, 1) per day are recognized and modified within certain range to simulate the correct air temperature of that room according to the measured data. If the calibration period for this example was 2 days with 4 possible settings at each point the number of combinations that would exist is:

$$Permutations_{with\ repetition} = n^r$$

Where:

n = is the number of possible settings

r = is the number of parameters ($2\ days \times 4\ \frac{parameters}{day} = 8\ parameters$)

Hence:

$$Permutations_{with\ repetition} = 4^8$$

$$Permutations_{with\ repetition} = 65,536$$

If the simulation period was 7 days, the possible combinations would be 7.206×10^{16} . This fast-growing number of parameter-combinations can be handled by the GA principles avoiding the —frequently impossible—task of assessing each of

them. However, the proper judgement from the consultant is necessary in this step to define a reasonable number of parameters during the calibration period to avoid excessive computational costs in the optimisation task.

The variables to be optimised include but not limited to air temperature, efficiencies, heating and cooling loads, and energy demand.

Figure 6: Optimise tool screenshot. Source: Optimise.

With the adequate methodology and using these three subprograms altogether, it is possible to achieve a high level of calibration quality enough to comply with current calibration standards.

7.3. Energy in Time

“Energy in Time” (EiT), a large European research project within the 7th Framework Programme, aims to optimise the current building control techniques using building energy simulation software. By using this approach, it is possible to spot any inefficient operation while keeping a comfortable environment. The scope of the project includes data forecasting to simulate the future behaviour of the building under different control scenarios. This involve the following developments:

- Calibration techniques which will reduce the margin of calibration error to +/- 5% that is achieved by the use of sub-hourly data.
- Automated calibrated models, where the models will be matched to the energy audits to increase accuracy and reduce the calibration effort.

- Develop cloud-based calibrated energy models. (Coakley, Aird, Earle, Klebow, & Conaghan, 2016)

This work is a thorough documentation of the step 3 from Figure 7 regarding the calibration of the model in order to comply with the M&V requirements in the proposed methodology.

Figure 7: Energy in Time calibration workflow. This paper targets step 3. Source: (Conaghan, Earle, Mulrey, & Coakley, 2016).

This step is critical to the project as the control strategy scenarios are fully dependent on a reliable model that represents the real model accurately. Further information about other tasks of the project such as the data acquisition platform can be found at (FP7-NMP, 2016)

In the present document, the types, application, state-of-art calibration approaches, and M&V standards for BES are further explored in the literature review. Later, a novel calibration methodology is presented, and tested in one hotel in Finland using measured data. For this work, the IES Virtual Environment software (IES-VE) is used to simulate the thermal analysis of the case study, optimise is used to achieve the calibration metrics and the SCAN platform for the data acquisition from the building. Finally, conclusions are drawn regarding this approach and a discussion section is presented to describe the current limitations of the methodology and recommendations to tackle them.

8. LITERATURE REVIEW

8.1. Types of BES models

Building models can be broadly divided into law driven models and data driven models. Law driven models are based on physical principles to calculate the energy demand of building, whereas data driven models use the available historic data to drive forecasts which may predict the demand accurately. Data-driven models may be further sub-divided into black box models, grey-box models and detailed calibrated models (Coakley, Raftery, & Keane, 2014).

Both have different applications and downsides. Law-driven models simulate ideal conditions with the possibility of being biased depending on the person creating them and his/her technical expertise and experience. They are used for design simulations as well as to assess potential design improvements in terms of relative energy reductions.

On the other hand, Black box, grey box and calibrated models rely on measured data. Black box models are purely statistical and forecast data based on the provided inputs ignoring the actual interaction of the parameters within the building. Grey box models are set up using a combination of physical knowledge and statistics, taking into account a limited number of parameters of the building making them useful to assess their impact on the model (Bacher & Madsen, 2011). A typical example of grey-box models are the Resistance-Capacitance (RC) networks often used to assess the impact of microclimate in the energy demand of buildings (Martin, Afshari, Armstrong, & Norford, 2015). In general, they are very susceptible to faulty data, uncertainties and high modelling costs.

Finally, detailed model calibrations do not rely on statistical models to work, but use measured data as inputs (instead of default profiles) and the outputs of these models follow completely physical principles. These type of models allow the assessment of practically any building scenarios but require large amounts of data to properly work which is often difficult to obtain or inexistent.

Table 3: Summary of the type of BES models. Source: Adapted from (Coakley, Raftery, & Keane, 2014)

The presented methodology in this work is intended for a detailed model calibration given that all the inputs (directly measured and derived) are used to feed the building energy model and there is not relationship between the inputs and the outputs other than laws of physics. The advantage of this approach is that the model is simulating how the energy is transferred within the building, enabling the model to use it as “what if” model for practically any relevant variable such as glazing properties, free ventilation, temperature set-points, impact caused by the excess (or lack) of occupancy among others.

8.2. Applications for BES

The application of the BES can be divided initially into design or calibrated, depending whether the building is constructed or not. Table 4 shows a summary of the applications for BES and some referenced examples.

Table 4: Applications for design and calibrated building simulations. Source: adapted from (Claridge, 2004)

Type	Applications	Examples
Design Simulation	Design process	(Kalakul, Malakul, Siemanond, & Gani, 2014)
	Environmental labels	LEED®, EDGE, BREEAM, PassivHaus, ESTIDAMA, etc.
	Post-construction commissioning of new buildings	Requisite for some credits in LEED® for new construction (Turner & Frankel, 2008) (Berning, 2008).
	Ongoing commissioning	Use BIM-generated model to assess performance (Motawa & Carter, 2013)
Calibrated Simulation	Retro Commissioning	(Claridge, 2004) (Reddy, 2006)
	Ongoing commissioning	(Jagemar & Olsson, 2007) (Castro, n.d.) Use BIM-based calibrated models (Ham & Golparvar-Fard, 2015).
	New control code	IES-VE (Coakley et al., 2016)
	Environmental labels	Performance-based simulations: LEED® Dynamic Plaque (USGBC, 2016)

Nowadays, the use of building simulations is very common at the design stage, including the HVAC capacity design, but is rarely used during building commissioning or operation phase of the building life-cycle (BLC). However, it is believed that the use

of model during the post-occupancy phases of the BLC could help improve building performance and energy efficiency (Service, 2011). This idea has been there for twenty years but was implemented in very few and isolated cases (Claridge, 2004).

Also, a calibrated model can be used to explore a range of building scenarios, operational changes, building retrofitting, demand reduction measures, the impact of the user behaviour in the energy demand, and in general, allows us to know the impact of any decision before they are implemented. These scenarios can be used not only at building level but also at a larger scale, making a powerful tool to develop “smart cities” all over the world (Coakley, 2016).

8.3. Calibration approaches

There are obvious advantages of a calibrated model, but the required effort, time and computational costs make them still difficult to achieve in practice. In fact, existing buildings models are considered the new frontier for modelling due to the relative complexity, expertise needed, and lacks of enough (or non-existent) data that the model requires to come up with an accurate energy (Dirkes & Weaver, 2016)(Zhao & Magoulès, 2012).

There are few thorough documented approaches for calibration in real buildings, some of them are at experimental level, such as the twin houses in Germany, (Strachan & Heusler, 2014)(Strachan, Svehla, Heusler, & Kersken, 2014), and the rest are done at experimental level with very specific conditions that can be hardly applied in all buildings.

Based on the review of methods in (Coakley et al., 2014), four types of calibration are presented:

1. Manual, iterative and pragmatic.
2. Informative, graphical and comparative displays.
3. Based on special tests and analytical procedures.
4. Analytical/mathematical methods of calibration.

8.4. Calibration periods

The calibration period for any building model will vary depending on the use of the model, for instance a model used for a whole year assessment will require monthly utility bill data during one year at least.

On the other hand, models utilised to explore control strategies will require hourly or sub-hourly data also known as high-res data and given that a full year of high-res data is unlikely to have in the vast majority of buildings Short-term end-use monitoring (STEM) strategies are adopted. This is case of the work of (Kaplan, McFerran, Jansen, & Pratt, 1990) and (Soebarto, 1997), where short seasonal calibration periods –one month or two-week periods– are suggested instead of full year. This approach requires detailed and continuous monitored data only during the calibration periods, for example: two weeks in summer and two weeks in winter.

8.5. Measurement and Verification standards (M&V)

In the context of model calibration, the measurement and verification process consist on assessing the output of the simulation by comparing it to measured data using statistical measures.

The thoroughness of the calibration shall be defined by the expected usefulness of the model. In other words, it will depend on what the model is for, in order to avoid unnecessary effort.

The three more important standards for M&V are given by the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE), International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP) and the Federal Energy Management Program (FEMP). Each of these will be further described as they are critical for any building simulation engineer.

ASHRAE

The American Society of Refrigerant and Air-conditioning Engineers is an organisation created in 1894. HVAC, Energy modelling, and M&V guidelines and standards are set by this organisation and they are widely recognized not only in the United States but also in Canada, Latin America, Middle East, and Asia.

IPMVP

The International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP) is a framework that attempts to standardise the concept of M&V for buildings, part of the Efficiency Valuation Organisation (EVO).

FEMP

Federal Energy Management Program (FEMP) is an American initiative that aims the reduction of the energy consumption from the Federal Government of the United States of America, being the largest energy consumer of the country. (US Department of Energy (DOE), 2016)

The methods for assessing calibration performance are statistical indices that represent the performance of a model. The common representatives are:

Annual percentage error

This is the most basic index that measures the absolute error between the measured and calibrated data at the end of one-year period.

$$APE(\%) = \frac{\bar{m} - \bar{s}}{\bar{m}}$$

Where:

\bar{m} = average measured values.

\bar{s} = average simulated values.

Mean Bias Error (MBE)

$$MBE (\%) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} (m_i - s_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} (m_i)}$$

Where:

m_i = Measured value of each sample

s_i = Simulated value of each sample.

N_p = number of samples

Normal Mean Bias Error (NMBE)

$$NMBE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} (m_i - s_i)}{\bar{m} * (N_p - p)}$$

m_i = Measured value of each sample

s_i = Simulated value of each sample.

N_p = number of samples

p = number of predictor variables (1)

Coefficient of Variation of Root Mean Square Error (CVRMSE)

$$CV(RMSE) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} (m_i - s_i)^2}{(n - p)}}}{\bar{m}}$$

m_i = Measured value of each sample

s_i = Simulated value of each sample.

N_p = number of samples

p = number of predictor variables (1)

These 3 measures are often used to assess or quantify the level of calibration of the models (IBPSA, 2010).

Regarding to the criteria to define whether a model is calibrated, Table 5 shows a summary of the criteria for ASHRAE, IPMPBE and FEMP respectively.

Table 5: Criteria for calibrated models for different standards. Source: (Coakley et al., 2014)

	Monthly criteria (%)		Hourly criteria (%)	
	MBE	CVRMSE	MBE	CVRMSE
ASHRAE	5	15	10	30
FEMP	5	15	10	30

8.6. Genetic algorithms (GAs)

Genetic algorithm is a heuristic search and optimisation technique that uses an abstract version of the Darwinian evolution theory. In here, each model solution is called “chromosome” which in turn create a generation with a limited number of chromosomes, this is known as generation. Each chromosome must be assessed using a fitness parameter (objectives) which describes how good is the solution. The most “fit” solutions produce a successor population where their genetic material (parameters) is recombined to create a new generation which are expected to have an improved average fitness. This is an iterative process that continues till it reaches certain fitness criteria. GAs have been used form modelling and optimisation where the number of potential solutions are so large that brute computational force is impossible to use.(McCall, 2005).

Multi-objective, also known as multi-criteria genetic algorithm have been widely used for building design, some examples are found in Table 6.

Table 6: Different uses for GAs in the building energy models.

Stage	Objectives	References
Design stage	Balance up the energy cost and occupant thermal discomfort	(Wright, Loosemore, & Farmani, 2002) (Yu, Li, Jia, Zhang, & Wang, 2015)(Magnier & Haghighat, 2010)
	Life cycle assessment for environmental and economic criteria	(Wang, Zmeureanu, & Rivard, 2005) (Fonseca I Casas et al., 2015)
	HVAC design	(Mohamed, Ala, & Kai, 2009)
Existing building	School building retrofitting optimising for energy consumption,	(Asadi, Silva, Antunes, Dias, & Glicksman, 2014)

	retrofit cost, and thermal discomfort hours.	
	Scenarios for energy efficiency for sports facilities	(Petri et al., 2014)
	Estimating heating and cooling loads using a thermal network model	(Ji, Xu, Duan, & Lu, 2016)

According to reviewed literature, the use of the GAs for buildings energy models should be focused on improving the efficiency of search techniques and approximation methods for large-scale building optimization problems. Research is likewise required to compute the robustness in optimal solutions in order to improve building performance stability in existing buildings (Nguyen, Reiter, & Rigo, 2014).

9. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

First of all, it is important to understand the concept of building levels. These are: space, zone, component, system, and building. The level of detail in the calibration will increase with the amount of available data from upper levels, as described in Figure 8. For instance, a model with air temperature readings in the rooms (space level) and electricity bills (System level), will have less uncertainty than a model that only has electricity bills reported. This may seem obvious, however, the strategy to link these two variables in the building may greatly vary depending on the experience of the engineer, time available and main purpose of the model. In addition, there may not always be a direct equivalence between physically measured parameters and simulation variables such as: pressure in air ducts and percentage of valve opening for water loops.

Figure 8: Level of detail in the building calibration process. Source: (Maile, 2010) with pictures from the IES-VE.

To better understand this subdivision of the building, a rough description of each level is shown in Table 7. This division shall be applied to most of the buildings regardless their level of complexity.

Table 7: Description, scope and data of each level.

Level	Description
Building	Enclosure conditioned for the daily human activities.
System	This is the supply side. Includes heat pumps, boilers, thermal plants, active renewable systems, etc. All the HVAC networks are connected to these systems to condition the building.
Component	Parts of the HVAC system that are involved in fulfilling the demand from the zone. Air handling units, radiators, fans, heat exchangers are components.
Zone	Space(s) that are connected to the same HVAC system. The total load of the zone shall be fulfilled by the same fans and AHUs. Also, the air coming from the zones is mixed and in some cases returned to the space.
Space	Is a physical space with common characteristics where the air temperature is considered homogeneous. E.g. Toilet, Bedroom, corridor, closets, etc.

Figure 8 demonstrates the general methodology for this work. The arrows represent the starting point and the process will be gradually moving from left to right while ascending through the building levels.

Figure 9: High level methodology.

This methodology does not consider the work that must be done to obtain weather data, the creation of the building model as well as the HVAC model. It starts at the moment when a model (e.g. the one used for the design stage of the building) is compared against measured data and requires a calibration process in order to be useful after construction completion.

The first step is to obtain the most important calibration parameters by performing a sensitivity analysis. Then, the most important variables will be classified into the previously identified levels. Each level shall have a well-defined boundary condition that consists on the inputs and outputs identified or relevant on each of them, reducing uncertainty. Finally, the variables that are known or measured are added to the model whereas the unknown ones will be derived where possible, by using a bounded optimisation approach. Figure 10 represents the process in a simplified manner.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Measured inputs} + \text{Unknown inputs} \rightarrow f(\text{Building/System/Component/Zone/Space}) = \text{Error } (\Delta) \\
 & \text{Solve for Error } (\Delta) = 0, \text{ using unknown inputs}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 10: Methodology to derive unknown inputs through the building levels.

9.1. Sensitivity analysis

Given the vast available parameters in a building energy simulation model, it is important to define which are the most relevant ones given the available data, expertise and time. Also, this parameter discrimination shall help the consultant to decide which sensors and type of data are critical to carry out the analysis.

The process to obtain relevant model parameters consist in two stages: (1) heuristic selection and (2) sensitivity analysis, as described in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Process to obtain relevant model parameters.

The heuristic selection is done using the expertise of the consultant, taking into account: type of building, geometry, availability of dynamic and static data, resources allocated for the task, intend of the model and experiences on previous model calibrations. The result is a subset of parameters that are relevant for the model but their impact on the calibration is still unknown, hence the list is unranked at this stage.

The second step is the actual sensitivity analysis to understand how independent variables impact in a particular dependent variable within the model. In order to fairly compare relative parameter sensitivities, a normalisation method is used. For each parameter, the standard deviation of each simulation output is calculated. For a finite data set x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N , with each value having the same probability, in a population of N values, with a mean value μ , the standard deviation σ is

$$\text{Standard Deviation, } \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}$$

The coefficient of variation (CV) is defined as the ratio of the standard deviation σ to the mean μ . These values are calculated for input and out variables of the model

$$\text{Coefficient of Vairation, } CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu}$$

The factors are applied in the parameter input value coefficient of variation (CV) in order to create a set of normalised indices for a fair comparison using the below formula:

$$\text{Normalised Sensitivity Index (NMI)} = \frac{\sigma_{y(x)}}{\text{Max } \sigma_y} / CV_{i(x)}$$

Finally, the overall sensitivity index considers each of the normalised ones, using the mean value, or average:

$$\text{Overall Sensitivity Index (NMI)} = \text{Average(NMI)}$$

These are plotted as a clustered bar chart, indicating the relative importance of each input variable with respect to the chosen model output variables (Conaghan et al., 2016).

9.2. Space and Zone level calibration

In this step, a closed system at the room or zone level with the simulated variables identical to the measured data is created. Rooms and areas are assigned: lighting gains, equipment gains, air temperature and air flow as it is in reality. Then, the simulated return air temperature (RAT) is compared to the measured one, and the missing or extra gains, are assumed to be part of the infiltration and/or occupancy profile. This step can be done manually or using genetic algorithms (GAs) through the tool “optimise”. This process is described in Figure 12.

$$Components + Environment + Internal gains + Unknowns \rightarrow f(\text{Zone model}) = T_{ra,s}$$

Solve for $\Delta T_{ra,(m-s)} = 0$ (or for time series, we minimise $CVRMSE$) using unknowns

Figure 12: Example of space and zone level calibration. Green rectangles represent directly measured data. Blue are simulated data. Yellow is derived.

Before moving forward is very important to achieve certain level of calibration for the air temperature, as the rest of the process will depend on the successful representation of the heat transfer within the zones. Recommendations for calibration of model zone air temperature were not found in the literature reviewed. However, the calibration of the air temperature of the room enables the model to accurately represent the indoor conditions which in turn can be used to explore the impact of energy saving conservation measures within the zone such as free cooling, facade retrofitting, external shadings, among others. Based on the experience gained on this methodology, the following criteria is suggested:

$$CVRMSE_{air\ temperature} \leq 3.5\%$$

Based on an average temperature of 24 °C, a $CVRMSE_{air\ temperature} \leq 3.5\%$ represents an average error less than 1 °C during the calibration period, which can be adjusted in the control strategy in the following level of calibration.

In this level of calibration air ducts can be included but it is always to recommendable to refer to HVAC drawings instead of assuming that they are unknown variables. Also, the U-value of the ducts shall be defined at this level.

9.3. Component level calibration

This step can be subdivided into two main sections:

- Control Strategy, and;
- Efficiencies & losses.

$Components + Environment + Efficiency + Unknown\ variables \rightarrow f(HVAC) = L_{c,s}$
 Solve for $\Delta L_{c,(m-s)} = 0$ (or for time series, we minimise CVMSE and NMBE) using unknowns

Figure 13: Component level calibration methodology.

9.3.1. Control strategy

The control strategy is set up at this point and must be defined for each HVAC network in the building. The control strategy consists of understanding and imitating how the supply air temperature, air flow is defined. Regarding the air temperature, usually it is defined based on the return air temperature (RAT), the outdoor air temperature (OAT). For the airflow, operational schedules, CO2 alarms and ducts pressure are key drivers.

After this step, the model shall be able to imitate the measured temperature set-points and air flows automatically, though exceptions may be found: if there is an exceptional heating/cooling requirement and the set point was defined manually, the control strategy cannot be simulated the same when the airflow is controlled by the pressure of the air ducts.

9.3.2. Equipment efficiency

In this step the efficiencies of the components are adjusted in order to match the simulated loads with the measured ones, this is especially important for heat exchangers. Other component specification shall be defined in this level such as fan power, and minimum airflow of any existing bypass.

9.4. System level calibration

At the system level, the real energy management shall be calibrated consulting the staff that is responsible of its supervision. The idea is to link the demand side with the supply side through the COP and the heat sources/heat pumps management should be derived with measured data. A general diagram of the process is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Step 3, at the system level, the coefficient of performance of the heat pumps, boilers, and renewable energy sources is calibrated.

This step can be very simple as having a performance curve depending on the percentage of energy demand. However, some larger projects may include several heat pumps, ice storage systems and they can have a sequential order of initiation. Figure 15, shows an example of an advanced thermal plant (system level) that included 5 heat pumps and two of them are connected to an ice storage system that are designed to avoid the need of electricity during the morning time, which is when the

electricity is more expensive. Hence, charge and discharge schedules would be required to be assigned to the model additionally.

Figure 15: There is a control strategy that defines the order in which the heat pumps will work depending on the demand side of the building. Also, there is a charge and discharge period for the ice storage system and shall be adjusted to reduce the demand when the cost of the electricity is higher. Source: IES-VE

9.5. Measurement and Verification (M&V)

Finally, M&V at the load or at the system level shall be performed to assess the level of calibration taking as reference the previously mentioned criteria.

Figure 16: Step 4, depending on the scope and nature of the project, the M&V shall be carried out using either loads or energy data by comparing measured and simulated results.

9.6. Data sources per building level

In order to “feed” the model correctly, the data used for each level is critical. In this work, we divided the source of data as: direct, derived and references. “Direct” refers to direct measurements such as temperature and energy consumption (kW), “derived” uses direct measurements and other assumptions to be calculated, such as the one proposed in this work. Finally, “referenced” means that this input is taken from factsheets, journals, standards, etc. This table is a guideline of the “best practices” to obtain data for each building level:

- ⊕ Most convenient and reliable source for this data, also most of the time is feasible both for time and budget.
- ⊙ May turn out difficult and it is reliable under certain conditions, data post-processing may be required and/or experience required to detect data faults.
- ⊖ Not recommended, and usually is not economically feasible and/or the reliability is low.

Table 8: Typical source of data for different building levels.

Level	Data	Source		
		Direct	Derived	Referenced
Building	Electricity	⊕ Electricity meters with logger (hourly resolution)	⊙ Monthly utility bills used to obtain hourly demand (Smith, Fumo, Luck, & Mago, 2011)	⊖ Yearly energy consumption, per m2 based on building typology and energy consumption surveys. (BEIS, 2016)(Pérez-Lombard, Ortiz, & Pout, 2008)(Brockett & Berkeley, 2000)
	Primary energy	⊖ N/A	⊕ Utility bills combined with schedule use.	⊖ Yearly energy consumption, per m2 based on building typology and energy consumption surveys. (BEIS, 2016)(Pérez-Lombard et al., 2008)(Brockett & Berkeley, 2000)
System	Electricity use	⊕ Electricity meters	⊙ Use total electricity demand and subtract non-system energy.	⊖ Manufacturer's data sheets
	Gas consumption	⊕ Heat meters	⊙ Use total primary energy demand and subtract non-system energy.	⊖ Building energy surveys (Pan, Huang, & Wu, 2007)

	COP	⊖ Measurements to determine instant efficiency.	⊕ Spot tests to determine: seasonal efficiency, deliver efficiency and coefficient of System performance (BS EN 14511-2:2013)	⊕ Manufacturer's data sheets
	Water flowrate	⊕ BEMS data	⊕ Spots check for the calibrated season	⊕ Building surveys
	Supply and return water temperature	⊕ BEMS data	⊕ Seasonal Spot measurements	⊖ Manufacturer's factsheet
	Chilled/hot water loop losses	⊖ Measurements to determine instant losses.	⊕ Spot tests.	⊕ Defaults Losses (2-10%)
	Control strategy (pumps)	⊕ Historical monitoring to understand the control strategy	⊕ Queries with facility managers.	⊖ Defaults functioning of the system
	Design parameters	⊖ N/A	⊕ Adjust design parameters according to the current state of the system	⊕ Design parameters of the system
	Component	Efficiencies	⊖ Instant efficiency may be misleading	⊕ Use BEMS data to obtain efficiency of the calibration period

	Control strategy	⊕ Observing the BEMS while checking air temperature readings.	⊕ Use historical BEMS data to derive the control strategy	⊕ Check the building energy management system
Zone and space	Cooling and heating load	⊖ N/A	⊕ Heat transfer formulas using BEMS data	⊕ Using weather data to estimate the expected cooling load (Mui & Wong, 2007). Using thermal network model (Ji et al., 2016).
	Air temperature Set-points	⊕ Actual observed set point	⊕ Set point reported	⊖ Default set-points: winter 21 °C and summer 25 °C
	Air flow	⊕ Actual observed set point	⊕ Spot tests during the same season	⊖ Standard ventilation recommendations. (De Dear & Brager, 2002) (Bohanon, 2010)
	Radiator set-points and mid-band	⊕ Actual observed set point	⊕ Set point reported	⊖ Default set-points: winter 18-22 °C
	Infiltration	⊖ Permeability tests (Pinto, Viegas, & de Freitas, 2011)	⊕ Derived from air temperature or other readings. (Iordache & Catalina, 2012)	⊕ (CIBSE Guide A, 2006)
	Air ducts	⊖	⊕	⊕ Drawings

			Conduct an audit to check the real status of the air ducts.	
Occupancy	 National calculation methodology (Communities & Local Government, 2008)			
Equipment	 Equipment use standards according the building typology (ASHRAE, 2016) (Communities & Local Government, 2008)			
Lighting	 Lighting demand standards according the building (ASHRAE, 2016)(Communities & Local Government, 2008)			
Construction material properties	 Building drawings			

9.7. Calibration periods

The calibration period for this approach will vary depending on the use of the model. However, the STEM strategies are followed in order to have short calibration periods that enable our model to take full advantage of the high resolution data from the BMS.

For instance, if the purpose of the model is to identify the optimal control strategy of the cooling system only during summer, the calibration period is expected to happen during 2 weeks within the summer months. It is critical that the heating system is shut down during the whole period to avoid adding extra noise to the model. The strategy is similar during winter calibration periods. Finally, if a whole-year simulation is required, an extra calibration period –noted as “transition calibration”– is needed to characterize the building control strategy when both the heating and cooling system is required in different times of the day. Ideally, a whole-year energy simulation would need 6 weeks in total of high resolution data. This approach is based on a parameter reduction calibration approach adapted from the work of (Bronson, Hinchey, Haberl, & O’Neal, 1992), (Hadley, 1993) and (Raftery, Keane, & O’Donnell, 2011). This approach can be scaled up to larger or smaller calibration periods depending on the available data and resources to carry out the model calibration.

Figure 17: Three critical calibration periods during the year following the sort-team end user methodology.

Finally, when more than one calibration period assessed is critical to classify constant and dynamic parameters. Whereas constant parameters practically do not change along the year such as U-values, dynamic ones may greatly vary and must be monitored. Examples of dynamic and constant parameters are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Constant and dynamic parameters across the calibration periods.

Constant	Dynamic
Physical properties of materials	Room set points
Geometry	Free cooling ventilation strategies
Infiltration ³	Occupancy trends
Thermal inertia	HVAC on/off schedule
Reflectivity of materials ⁴	Control strategy

³ Only in buildings that are considered highly air tight.

⁴ Assuming that proper façade cleaning tasks are carried out along the year

10.CASE STUDY: LEVI HOTEL

In the present document, the calibration and assessment of Levi hotel is shown in a detailed manner. This building is one of the four calibrated models for Energy in Time. One of the particularities of the building is the number of sensors installed in it, more than 22,000. However, throughout the steps of the methodology only the most critical sensors are used in order to keep the calibration process within the scheduled time and budgeted effort.

Figure 18: Levi Panorama Hotel. Source (GoLevi.fi, 2016)

Figure 19: Virtual model in the IES-VE.

A high level description is presented in Table 10. Area, geographic location and information related to the energy consumption is included.

Table 10: General description of the two case-study buildings.

	LEVI
Main use	Hotel
Location	Helsinki, Sanomatalo, Finland
Latitude	67.8N
Longitude	24.8E
ASHRAE Zone	Zone 8: Sub-Artic/Artic
Year of construction	2010
Floor area	15,227 m ²
Number of floors	7 + Basement
Users	1000
Type of calibration	Whole building
Number of sensors available for calibration	22,000 (shortlisted to 220)
Measured data resolution	Every 10 minutes
Electricity demand (MWh)	1 387
Heating demand (MWh)	2 257
Energy saving strategies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. District heating 2. Ground heating system 3. Solar heating system 4. Ground water heating/cooling (bored wells and sprinkler pool) 5. Condensed heat recovery system

To put this building into context, the following table describes Levi as needed to use this methodology.

Table 11: Levi breakdown to match the proposed mythology.

Level	Number
Building	1 hotel building
System	4 systems: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. District heating 2. Ground heating system 3. Solar heating system 4. Ground water heating/cooling (bored wells and sprinkler pool)
Component	Independent components: 8 HVAC networks and 3 underfloor heating systems
Zone	8 zones, each of them connected to one of the HVAC networks.
Space	1408 spaces including toilets, rooms, underfloor rooms, ceiling voids, corridors, restaurant, storage and bars.
Calibration period (s)	Only summer

10.1. Levi: Sensitivity analysis

For the case study, a considerable large amount of data was available for the calibration. The subset of parameters selected are shown in the annex section in Table 19.

Once the parameters were chosen by the consultant, the sensitivity analysis for Levi was carried out the parameters with respect to their impact on five key model outputs:

- Total energy [MWh]
- Total System Energy [MWh]
- Boilers Energy [MWh]
- Chillers Energy [MWh]
- Room Air Temperature [°C]

The normalised sensitivity analysis for Levi is ranked in Figure 20. This figure is used to rank them based on their relative importance and relevance to the model.

Figure 20: Levi – Normalised Sensitivity Indices. Source: WP2 deliverable 2.4 EIT

These parameters are now classified to its respective zone and the source of this data is defined, as shown in Table 12. Although occupancy does not appear to a driver variable, it is important to be defined due to its relationship with the domestic hot water demand (DHW).

Table 12: Classification of variables per level as well as its source.

Level	Data	Source		
		Direct	Derived	Referenced
Component	Efficiencies (AAHX_sensible effectivnss)		⊕ Use BEMS data to obtain efficiency of the calibration period	
	Control strategy	⊕		⊙

		Observing the BEMS while checking air temperature readings.		Check the building energy management system
Zone and space	Cooling and heating load		⊕ Heat transfer formulas using BEMS data	
	Air temperature Set-points	⊕ Observed from the departing air temperature		
	Air flow (Air_flow)	⊕ Observed from the departing air temperature		
	Radiator setpoints and mid-band (Radiator_midband)	⊕ Observed from the BMS		
	Infiltration		⊙ Derived from air temperature or other readings using manual approximation	
	Air ducts (Duct_area)			⊕ Drawings
	Occupancy		⊙ 6 out of 8 Derived from the return air	⊙ 2 zones use standards from

			temperature of each zone using GAs	the national calculation methodology
	Equipment	⊕ Electric meters		
	Lighting	⊕ Electric meters		
	Construction material properties		⊕ Auditing the building.	

All the data was obtained from the BEMS of Levi. Heating loads were derived using the following formula directly in SCAN:

$$Q_{heating\ season} = \dot{m} \times C_p \times (T_{supplied} - T_{return})$$

Where:

$$\dot{m} \left(\frac{kg}{s} \right) = flow \left(\frac{m^3}{h} \right) \times 0.27778 \left(\frac{h}{m^3} * \frac{kg}{s} \right)$$

And

$$C_p = 4.187 \frac{kJ}{kg}$$

The resulting loads are given in kW, so they can be compared directly to the simulation outputs. Zone and level calibration shall start after defining the source of all necessary data.

10.2. Levi: Space and Zone level calibration

For Levi, given the large number of rooms and the complexity of the model, the calibration is done from the zone level. However, air temperature sensors in 50% of the rooms are installed, providing an extra verification step demonstrating that the room air temperatures are adjusted when the return are temperature of the whole zone is adjusted. This assumption is fair given that the rooms in each of the zones

share same the type of use. The calibration scheme for this level in Levi is shown in Figure 21.

$$\text{Components} + \text{Environment} + \text{Internal gains} + \text{Unknowns} \rightarrow f(\text{Zone model}) = T_{ra,s}$$

Solve for $\Delta T_{ra,(m-s)} = 0$ (or for time series, we minimise CVRMSE) using unknowns

Figure 21: Zone level calibration for Levi.

For the zone level calibration, all the 8 HVAC networks were assigned directly the airflow and air temperature set-points, in order to calculate the infiltration (ACH) and occupancy gains (kW).

Figure 22: Measured and simulated airflow in the VE. Source: IES-VE

The infiltration for each of the zones is defined using a manual approach, consisting on the observation of the air temperatures when the occupancy and equipment and lighting gains is considered constant and there is not presence of solar gains. Hence the observed period is usually around 12:00am to 4:00am. This process is used by consultants to estimate the air leakage and was the most convenient strategy for Levi. The summary of the air leakage for each zone is shown in Table 13

Table 13: Type of zones covered in each HVAC network and air leakage for each zone. Source: IES-VE.

HVAC	Zone type	Infiltration (ACH)
TK301	Restaurant	0.2
TK302	Administrative offices	0.2
TK303	Kitchen	1
TK304	Restaurant	0.4
TK305	Hotel rooms	0.2
TK306	Offices	0.2

TK307	Restaurant	0.2
TK308	Corridors	0.2

Then, the sub program Optimise is used to adjust the occupancy pattern in order to match the measured and simulated return air temperature (RAT) for each of the 8 HVAC networks.

In the IES-VE, occupancy pattern can be described using a “free-form profile” or FFP, which is a time-series type of data that can describe any type of behaviour of the building along the time. One occupancy profile is linked to each of the 8 HVAC networks, and Optimise shall manage to derive the occupancy from each of the return air temperature time-series data. This process requires 8 individual optimisations where each of the FFPs is modified to match the return air temperature known as “Exhaust entering dry-bulb temperature” in Apache HVAC. “Optimise” was adapted to fulfil this task exclusively for this work and it requires the IDs of the FFPs and the components’ ID that contain the return air temperature. Table 14 was used to set up each of the optimisations.

Table 14: FFP ID and component ID in the IES-VE to be used as an input in Optimise.

HVAC network	Zone level		
	FFP ID for Occupancy	Measured	Exhaust entering dry-bulb temperature
TK301	FFRM0445	TK301 RAT COMP	HR000130
TK302	FFRM0446	TK302 RAT COMP	HR000132
TK303	FFRM0430	TK303 RAT COMP	HR000133
TK304	FFRM0448	TK304 RAT COMP	HR000134
TK305	FFRM0428	TK305 RAT COMP	HR000135
TK306	Uses NCM standard due to the lack of RAT data		
TK307	Uses NCM standard due to the lack of RAT data		
TK308	FFRM0429	TK308 RAT COMP	HR000138

The optimisation process is used with generations of about the size of the variables due to the time it takes for each simulation to be completed, around 145 seconds each one as shown in Figure 23 obtained from optimise.

Figure 23: Simulation time for the model. Source: Optimise

The status of the optimisation can be seen in the user-interface of optimise, in here, the best CVRMSE, R2 and NMBE are plotted to have an idea of when is the right moment to finalise the optimisation, Figure 24.

Figure 24: Optimisation process of the return air temperature for one of the HVAC network (TK308). The blue line corresponds to the measured RAT whereas the yellow, pink and red lines are the best guesses for each of the criteria. Source: Optimise

After the optimisation process, optimised air temperature for the HVAC network TK308 is presented in the following figure. For this work, a margin of $\pm 1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ is allowed.

Figure 25: Return air temperature for TK308. Green is measured, the blue line represents the temperature before it was optimised, and the red line is the final temperature profile. Source: IES-VE.

Due to the availability of data, 6 out of 8 HVAC networks were optimised at the zone level using Optimise. In Figure 26, TK305 which corresponds to the hotel is shown both for supply and return air temperature, to provide a better idea of how the model is actually responding to the real conditions in the hotel. The CVRMSE is 2.54%.

- Exhaust entering dry-bulb temperature: Air-to-air heat enthalpy exchanger - HR000135 (Levi_B_01.aps)
- Exhaust entering dry-bulb temperature: Air-to-air heat enthalpy exchanger - HR000135 (LEVI HOTEL - FINLAND-20160601-20160802.apm)
- Air temperature: layer 0/214 (Levi_B_01.aps)
- Air temperature: layer 0/214 (LEVI HOTEL - FINLAND-20160601-20160802.apm)

Figure 26: For HVAC TK305 (hotel). The model is assigned the measured air temperature (bottom part) and simulated return air temperature (red) shall be matched as possible to the measured one (blue).

Although, return air temperature of TK305 is the only one that is assessed. Improvements in the individual rooms of the hotel can be observed, meaning that in average, all the room temperatures are somehow optimised using this approach making the model more realistic, regardless of the high number of rooms in the model, Figure 27.

Figure 27: Room level calibration using room air temperature data before (red) and after (black) adjusting occupancy and air infiltration. Notice how the simulation is matching the measured air temperature.

Finally, the occupancy pattern for this specific network is shown in Figure 28. 8 occupancy patterns were defined in this task: 6 using the optimisation approach, and the remaining 2 using default standards of the National calculation methodology.

Figure 28: Optimised occupancy pattern in the FFP. Source: IES-VE.

10.3. Levi: Component level calibration

For Levi, the component level calibration the building control strategy and heat exchanger will be calibrated to match the total heating coil loads.

$Components + Environment + Efficiency + Unknown\ variables \rightarrow f(HVAC) = L_{c,s}$
 Solve for $\Delta L_{c,(m-s)} = 0$ (or for time series, we minimise CVRMSE and NMBE) using unknowns

Figure 29: Component level calibration for Levi.

However, to improve the accuracy of the model, each of the heating coil load will be assessed individually using Optimise to verify that the control strategy is the right one as well to define the efficiency of the heat exchanger. In the following table, the sensible load ID for each heating coil is listed as it is required by Optimise to proceed with the optimisation.

Table 15: Component ID of the heating coil in the IES-VE to be used as an input in Optimise.

HVAC network	Component	
	Measured	Sensible load
TK301	TK301 Heating Coil Load	HC002820
TK302	TK302 Heating Coil Load	HC002826
TK303	TK303 Heating Coil Load	HC002828
TK304	TK304 Heating Coil Load	HC002830
TK305	TK305 Heating Coil Load	HC002832
TK306	TK306 Heating Coil Load	HC002834
TK307	TK307 Heating Coil Load	HC002836
TK308	TK308 Heating Coil Load	HC002838

10.3.1. Control strategy

The strategy was obtained from the BEMS of the hotel using the online platform.

Figure 30: Control strategy followed by the BEMS. Source: Levi BEMS

It is worth mentioning that is not always the case that these strategies are strictly followed in real life, so engineering judgement and constant monitoring is necessary to make sure that real control strategies are being simulated.

Table 16: Summary of control strategies per each HVAC network.

HVAC network	Temperature set point control strategy	Airflow rate control strategy
TK301	Proportional control based on the return air temperature and air flow rate.	Controlled to keep the duct pressure but CO2 sensors are installed in the restaurant and bar, up to 500 ppm.
TK302	Proportional control based on the return air temperature and air flow rate.	Controlled to keep the duct pressure but CO2 sensors are installed in the bar area, up to 500 ppm.
TK303	Proportional control based on two room's temperature (assumed as RAT in the model)	Controlled to keep the duct pressure.

TK304	Proportional control based on return air temperature.	Controlled to keep the duct pressure.
TK305	Proportional control based on the outdoor air temperature.	Controlled to keep the duct pressure.
TK306	Proportional control based on return air temperature.	Controlled to keep the duct pressure.
TK307	Proportional control based on return air temperature.	Controlled to keep the duct pressure.
TK308	Proportional control based on return air temperature, however manual Setpoint are overriding this control strategy, hence can't be simulated (thus, FFP used)	Controlled to keep the duct pressure.

10.3.1. Efficiency and losses

In Levi, the heat exchangers shall be adjusted to their real efficiency. To do this, the calibrated return air temperature and the assigned building control strategy are critical. Heating coil loads are optimised individually using the same approach as for occupancy.

Figure 31 represents an actual HVAC network in Levi whereas Figure 32 is the representation of the same network in Apache HVAC. The component to be calibrated at this stage is the heat exchanger circled in the red in both figures.

Figure 31: BEMS of the HVAC network TK305 in Levi. Source: Levi BEMS

Figure 32: HVAC network TK305 in the VE. Return air temperature (RAT) and supply air temperature (SAT). Source: Adapted from IES-VE.

The optimisation was done using comparing the heating loads in the air handling units, in Figure 33 the optimisation for the HVAC TK308 is shown.

Figure 33: Component level calibration for TK308.

The optimisation was done in the 8 heat exchangers and in Table 17 the results are listed in percentage of efficiency for recovering sensible loads.

Table 17: Efficiency of the heat exchangers according to the measured data.

Network	Previous (%)	Calibrated (%)
TK301	72	41.07
TK302	60	73.68
TK303	60	89.95
TK304	59	2.14
TK305	30	22.04
TK306	60	89.4
TK307	60	40.68
TK308	60	2.5

These results were updated in the IES-VE model. Notice that TK304 and TK308 resulted in a very low efficiency HX, meaning that during the calibration period this heat exchanger was not being used, in other words, the air is being bypassed directly to the heating coils suggesting a fault in the building control strategy which shall be addressed with the building facility manager.

10.4. Levi: System level calibration

System level calibration is not required for the scope of Energy in time, and also data at this level was not measured, hence, it cannot be performed.

10.5. Levi: M&V

The scope of the energy in time project is limited to the calibration at the component level. Thus the M&V presented is based on the load of the building, which is explained in Figure 34 in the context of the current methodology.

Figure 34: M&V for Levi is done at the component level only.

Finally, the total heating loads of the 8 HVAC networks and the simulated loads are plotted together for the purpose of comparison. The M&V metrics are assessed in the following section.

Figure 35: Heating coils for all the AHU's for LEVI. Measured (blue) and simulated (red). Source: IES-VE

11. VALIDATION OF RESULTS THROUGH M&V

Using the indices described in the literature review, an M&V assessment is for the total heating coil loads of the hotel during the calibration period. A summary of the calibration is shown in Table 18.

Table 18: Summary of the calibration for Faro and Levi.

	LEVI
Sub hourly data	10 min
Simulation time step	6 min
Reporting interval for M&V	60 min
Calibration period	28 th of June to 6 th of July.
Number of data points (N)	216
Annual percentage error (%)	2.42
NMBE (%)	2.57
CVRMSE (%)	29.2

As it can be observed, both NMBE and CVRMSE are within the ASHRAE and FEMP calibration standards, hence the model is considered to be calibrated.

12. CONCLUSIONS & DISCUSSION

BES models are a powerful tool to reduce the carbon emissions of the building sector by exploiting their ability to forecast the impact of changes in the building fabric and operational control, thus aiding in the selection of optimal solutions for both new and existing buildings. To achieve this, several building energy simulation software packages exist in the market.

Black, grey and detailed models can be used to forecast energy demand. However, detailed models are potentially the most powerful option. Calibration of BES models is the current challenge in the industry as it faces an enormous barrier in complying with most of the M&V standards, such as lack of explicit standards for calibration criteria, expense and time needed, getting the right simplified model, faulty data, uncertainty and the lack of integrated tools.

This work presents a calibration methodology that uses building levels to calibrate these elements individually, reducing the degree of uncertainty. Missing data is derived using either manual engineering expertise or the optimisation approach with the tool "Optimise". The model is simulated using the IES-VE and the data is obtained using SCAN, an online platform for data acquisition.

A hotel in Finland is used as the case-study, 8 zones, and 8 HVAC networks were calibrated and the final M&V assessment was done at the load level. The final calibration measures were: NMBE of 2.57% and CVRMSE: 29.2%.

In general, is fair to say that calibrated models are becoming a common practice for the following reasons:

1. Granular data is increasingly available to measure and archive measurements for building performance simulations during the building life cycle. Also, the industry is moving toward performance-based certification e.g. LEED® Dynamic Plaque, Figure 36.

2. Increase in adoption of construction technologies such as BIM, makes it easier to develop operational models. Already mandatory in some countries such as the United Kingdom (Volk, Stengel, & Schultmann, 2014).
3. Availability of data through the installation of BEMS (mostly in new buildings) is more common every day in the industry, enabling the energy simulation industry to take advantage for the creation of accurate calibrated models in an automated or semi-automated manner.

Figure 36: Performance-based LEED® Dynamic Plaque certification that requires ongoing data readings. Source: (USGBC, 2016)

Advantages of having a calibrated model include but are not limited to:

1. BES models can help to find the most cost-efficient energy saving practices for different buildings types. Hence, it will make them a more common practice.
2. Optimised control strategies. Building simulations allows building managers to investigate a larger range of options that are not feasible in real life. Assuring an informed solution that will increase the confidence in the green building industry.
3. Calibrated models allow building owners to investigate operational changes without impacting occupants or expose them to uncomfortable indoor environments.

Due to inherent complexity of producing calibrated building energy models, some areas provide an opportunity for further development and research to reduce the effort required in future calibrations. The ones detected while this work was carried out are mentioned in the following sub-sections.

12.1. Response time and damping effect

In reality, the time it takes for the air to go through pipes from the rooms to the HVAC systems as well as the thermal inertia of the ducts are impacting the differential between measured and simulated data, which in turn impacts the M&V indices. A damping effect was observed in the return air temperature mainly in the largest HVAC system, the one corresponding to the hotel rooms, Figure 37 .

Also, furniture and other objects in the rooms will impact the behaviour of the return air temperature. This time lag, cannot be simulated within any existing building energy performance simulation tool.

Figure 37: Air-temperature damping observed in the HVAC network TK305.

To tackle this issue, an in-depth computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis or a high resolution assessment as the one described in (Hand, 2016) shall be carried out but further research is required to assess the needed work to balance up between time spent and quality of the model.

12.2. Occupancy gains

Occupancy gains are often main drivers in the BES, however not much attention is given to this concern. Building models often use occupancy standards given by local regulations, such as the National Calculation Methodology (NCM) in the UK (Communities & Local Government, 2008) which for this calibration approach, were not useful. Fortunately, according to (Oldewurtel, Sturzenegger, & Morari, 2013) additional occupancy gains predictions do not provide significant energy savings potential, however a long-term occupancy profile shall be defined for each study case.

12.3. Infiltration

Currently, infiltration is considered to be a constant value for most of the BESS. Depending on the nature of the building, it may be a major driver in the cooling and heating loads. During the calibration process, it was noticed that during the operational hour of the HVAC the infiltration was considerable higher than when the system was not functioning but no standard or guideline consulted addressed this issue.

Also, there are not existing guidelines for infiltration values for pilot zones, which shall include infiltration from the rest of the building as well as from outdoors. It is required a weighting methodology to define which infiltration is more critical.

12.4. M&V parameters for specific situations

M&V standards shall be considered only a guideline for models when full year simulation periods are not feasible and the measured data is not free of faults. For instance, N_p in these indices are expected to be either $N_{monthly} = 12$ or $N_{yearly} = 8760$, but there are calibration approaches that suggest the use of “calibration periods” –such as STEM–, generally summer and winter, that will have different N_p values.

Given that M&V standards are focused on yearly simulations, for many building energy simulations is impossible --or not needed-- to have such a long time span. For example, a calibrated model with an hourly resolution, would have to be one-year long to use these indices, which is highly unlikely, as models used for building control

require seasonal calibrated models, hence they are limited to weeks or less than 6 months.

Another potential exception for this calibration criteria is the purpose of the model. For instance, the same calibration criteria should not be applied to a model to be used for a 30-year retrofit assessment as that used for a model-predictive control project.

Regarding the measured data used for model calibrations, there are not guidelines on minimal data sets for different purposes. For instance, if you are doing a building retrofitting study, where the operation of the system must be explored for each of the retrofitting scenarios, there are not general guidelines on what level of metered data, calibration period(s) or what accuracy you should aim to achieve.

12.5. Uncertainty in the parameters

Although relevant parameters are shortlisted, all the input data will have a certain level of uncertainty. We can divide these parameters into static or dynamic and shall be addressed differently but the impact in the energy simulation is addressed in a similar manner. However, within the work in the thesis this is not addressed. In real life, the total time available to carry out a model calibration is limited and only uncertainty of the most relevant parameters shall be researched. This may include, real U-values, thermal bridging, faulty data from sensors, and any other heat transfer process that cannot be directly simulated with the existing building energy simulation software.

In future work, research is required to assign uncertainty to the ranked list of parameters, as proposed in (Coakley, 2014). The idea is to create a “weighted index” that takes into consideration the sensitivity analysis, uncertainty as well as the available data for each case, Figure 38. This index shall be used for shortlist the final parameter list.

Figure 38: Proposed strategy to address parameter uncertainty only for relevant parameters according to time and resources available.

Using information of the uncertainties of these inputs, an uncertainty analysis can be carried out. The final energy result will be similar to what is presented in Figure 39 and it will represent the potential energy results using the probably values of all the uncertain parameters within a confidence interval.

Figure 39: Energy forecast considering uncertainty.

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15.ANNEX-A SENSITIVITY ANALISIS

Table 19: Levi sensitivity variables. Source: (Conaghan et al., 2016)

		Component/Variable	Reference	Variance		
Component level	HVAC Terminal Units	Fresh Air Volume	Minimum Flow (l/s)	+/- 20%		
		Ductwork Heat Pick-up	Ductwork Heat Pick-up	+/- 30%		
		Ductwork Heat Pick-up	Ductwork Heat Pick-up	+/- 30%		
		Ductwork Heat Pick-up	Ductwork Heat Pick-up	+/- 20%		
		Radiator	Weight (Kg)	+/- 50%		
			Water Capacity (l)	+/- 50%		
			Radiant Fraction	+/- 50%		
		Underfloor Heating Zone	Flow at min sensed signal DB Temp	+/- 20%		
			Water Temperature to Underfloor	+/- 20%		
			Internal Ceiling: Concrete Screed Conductivity	+/- 50%		
			Internal Ceiling: Conductivity for insulation between floors	+/- 50%		
		Zone Set-Points	Zone Heating Set-Point	+/- 10%		
		Pre-Heat Coil	Heating Capacity	+/- 30%		
		Hot water loop	Hot water Supply temp (primary circuit)	+/- 50%		
			Hot water temp diff (primary circuit)	+/- 20%		
			Distribution Losses	+/- 20%		
		Zone & Space level	Constructions	Glazing/Roof lights	Conductivity	+/- 50%
					g-value	+/- 50%
Transmittance	+/- 50%					
Shortwave shading coefficient	+/- 50%					
Longwave shading coefficient	+/- 50%					
Total Shading	+/- 50%					
Ground/Exposed Floor	Conductivity		+/- 50%			
Internal Ceiling/Concrete Screed	Conductivity		+/- 50%			
Roof	Conductivity		+/- 50%			
External Wall	Conductivity		+/- 50%			
Room Variables	Infiltration (Fabric)		Air Leakage	+/-100%		
	Infiltration (Periodic)		Air Leakage due to openings	+/-100%		
	Lighting		Fluorescent Lighting Gain	+/- 50%		
	Equipment		Equipment Gain	+/- 50%		
	Occupancy	People Gain	+/-100%			

16.ANNEX-B SPACE AND ZONE LEVEL OPTIMISATION

Air temperature calibration.

TK301

TK302

TK303

TK304

TK305

TK308

